

Learning Compressed AIS Trajectories with VQ-VAE for Activity Classification

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Abstract—Automatic Identification System (AIS) data enables large-scale maritime monitoring but creates major challenges for storage and efficient downstream analysis because of its volume. Existing approaches typically treat trajectory compression and activity classification as separate problems, resulting in either loss of semantic information or high computational cost. To solve this issue, the proposed unified approach jointly learns compression and vessel activity classification using a Vector-Quantized Variational Autoencoder (VQ-VAE). Its model encodes each trajectory segment into a compact sequence of discrete indices, achieving up to $17.8\times$ compression while preserving information relevant to downstream tasks such as classification. A classifier then operates directly on the compressed representation, eliminating the need for reconstruction during inference.

Experiments on AIS trajectory data from fishing vessels show that the learned discrete representation is highly informative for detecting fishing behavior. A simple logistic regression on code usage histograms generated by the VQ-VAE achieves 99.48% accuracy and 97.64% macro F1, approaching the strongest sequence-model baseline (99.61%). At the same time, the model reconstructs trajectories with a mean positional error of 7.59 km while preserving key trajectory structures and behavioral patterns and maintaining full utilization of the compression codebook (512/512 active codes). This work demonstrates that discrete latent representations provide an effective and efficient interface for jointly addressing compression and behavioral inference in maritime trajectory data.

Index Terms—trajectory compression; trajectory reconstruction; activity classification; Vector-Quantized Variational Autoencoder (VQ-VAE); discrete representation learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Automatic Identification System (AIS) data provides rich spatiotemporal information about vessel movements, enabling a wide range of maritime monitoring and analysis applications. AIS data has been widely used for tasks such as traffic analysis, anomaly detection, route prediction, vessel behavior modeling, and maritime surveillance, as documented in recent surveys of the field [19]. However, AIS datasets are extremely large, creating significant challenges for storage, transmission, and real-time processing.

Existing approaches typically address compression and classification as separate problems. Geometric and signal-based trajectory compression methods reduce data size but often discard semantic information relevant to downstream tasks [11]. In contrast, deep learning methods for trajectory understanding and behavior classification typically operate on full-resolution trajectories, resulting in high computational and storage costs [21]. This separation limits the ability to efficiently deploy large-scale maritime analytics systems.

In this work, we propose a unified framework that jointly learns compression and classification using a Vector-Quantized Variational Autoencoder (VQ-VAE). The model learns a discrete latent representation that preserves both geometric structure and behavioral semantics. By encoding trajectories into compact sequences of discrete codes, the model enables efficient storage while supporting direct classification in the compressed domain.

Our key insight is that discrete latent representations can serve as a shared interface between compression and inference. Unlike continuous embeddings, discrete codes provide a structured and compact representation that can be reused across tasks without reconstruction.

Although our experimental evaluation focuses on AIS vessel trajectories and maritime activity recognition, the proposed framework is not domain-specific. The method can be applied to any sequential trajectory data that combines spatial and temporal information, including vehicle GPS traces, aviation trajectories, pedestrian mobility data, animal movement records, and sports tracking data. More broadly, it is suitable for applications where compact trajectory representations are required for downstream classification or behavioral inference.

The main contributions of this work are:

- A VQ-VAE framework achieving up to $17.8\times$ compression of AIS trajectories.
- Joint optimization for reconstruction and classification from a shared discrete representation.

- An effective training strategy for discrete trajectory modeling based on EMA quantization, improving codebook utilization and training stability in imbalanced settings.
- Empirical evidence that compact discrete representations preserve behaviorally relevant information and support accurate downstream classification directly in the compressed domain.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related work on trajectory representation learning and compression for maritime analytics. Section III presents the proposed methodology and model architecture. Section IV describes the experimental setup and reports the empirical results. Finally, Section V summarizes the findings of the study and outlines directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Trajectory analysis and trajectory compression have traditionally been studied separately. Early compression methods focused on reducing storage and transmission costs through geometric simplification and spatiotemporal redundancy removal while preserving path shape [16]. In parallel, trajectory analysis addressed clustering, similarity search, prediction, and behavior recognition using handcrafted features, distance measures, and probabilistic models [25]. These approaches, however, do not learn a shared representation that supports both compact storage and downstream inference.

More recent work treats trajectories as spatiotemporal sequences and learns reusable latent representations from labeled or unlabeled data [10]. In the maritime domain, Nguyen et al. [14] proposed a compress-then-classify variational recurrent model for AIS streams. Related autoencoder-based methods have been used for trajectory similarity [9], route compression [13], and trajectory prediction [1]. More broadly, transformer and self-supervised models dominate time-series representation learning, including masked reconstruction approaches [15], [23] and contrastive methods such as TS-TCC [2], TS2Vec [22], and TFC [24].

Most of these methods rely on *continuous* embeddings. While expressive, continuous representations require higher storage precision, are often less interpretable, and usually require an additional classifier or decoder. For compression-oriented settings, they must also be quantized or stored in floating-point form, reducing efficiency gains.

Recent time-series research has therefore revisited *discrete* representation learning through vector quantization. VQ-VAE [20] learns a finite codebook that maps encoder outputs to symbolic tokens, yielding compact and structured representations that are naturally compatible with lightweight classifiers. In time-series applications, discrete bottlenecks have been shown effective for generation [7], transfer across heterogeneous tasks [18], unsupervised domain adaptation [5], anomaly detection [8], and interpretable temporal modeling [3].

A key challenge is codebook collapse and unstable optimization. EMA updates and restart strategies improve utilization [6], while refinements to the straight-through estimator

[4], stochastic quantization [17], and finite scalar quantization [12] further stabilize discrete learning.

To the best of our knowledge, discrete representation learning has not been systematically explored for trajectory data. Existing trajectory models primarily rely on continuous embeddings, even when targeting compression and classification jointly. This work addresses that gap by learning compact discrete trajectory codes that directly support behavioral inference in the compressed domain.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed approach builds on the Vector-Quantized Variational Autoencoder (VQ-VAE) framework [20], which learns a discrete latent representation of sequential data. In contrast to conventional autoencoders that map an input to a continuous latent vector, VQ-VAE constrains the latent space to a finite set of learned prototype vectors, referred to as a *codebook*. Each encoder output is replaced by its nearest codebook entry, yielding a sequence of discrete indices that can be used as a compact symbolic representation of the input.

A. VQ-VAE Basics

Formally, let $X \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$ denote an input trajectory window with T timesteps and F features per timestep. An encoder f_θ maps X to a sequence of latent vectors

$$E = f_\theta(X) = [e_1, \dots, e_T], \quad e_t \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad (1)$$

where d is the latent dimensionality. VQ-VAE maintains a learned codebook

$$\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_K\}, \quad c_k \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad (2)$$

consisting of K discrete embedding vectors. For each timestep t , the continuous encoder output e_t is quantized by nearest-neighbor lookup:

$$z_t = \arg \min_{k \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \|e_t - c_k\|_2^2, \quad (3)$$

and the quantized latent vector is

$$q_t = c_{z_t}. \quad (4)$$

The discrete sequence $Z = [z_1, \dots, z_T]$ is the compressed representation, while $Q = [q_1, \dots, q_T]$ is the quantized embedding sequence passed to the decoder.

A decoder g_ϕ reconstructs the input from the quantized sequence:

$$\hat{X} = g_\phi(Q). \quad (5)$$

The overall model is therefore composed of three elements: (i) an encoder that produces continuous latent vectors, (ii) a vector quantizer that maps them to discrete codebook entries, and (iii) a decoder that reconstructs the original sequence from the quantized embeddings.

The standard VQ-VAE objective combines a reconstruction term with a commitment term that encourages encoder outputs to remain close to their selected codewords:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VQ}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{recon}} + \|\text{sg}[E] - Q\|_2^2 + \beta \|E - \text{sg}[Q]\|_2^2, \quad (6)$$

where $\text{sg}[\cdot]$ denotes the stop-gradient operator, $\|\cdot\|_2^2$ denotes the L_2 norm, and β controls the strength of the commitment loss. The first term measures how accurately the decoder reconstructs the input, the second updates the codebook toward the encoder outputs, and the third prevents encoder activations from drifting arbitrarily far from the selected codewords.

A key benefit of VQ-VAE is that the latent representation is discrete by construction. Each timestep is represented by an integer code index in $\{1, \dots, K\}$ rather than a dense floating-point vector, yielding a compact, structured representation that is directly reusable for downstream tasks. In our setting, the same discrete trajectory codes support compression, reconstruction, and behavioral inference within a unified framework.

B. Application of VQ-VAE to Trajectory Data

In this work, we apply the general VQ-VAE mechanism to trajectory data and augment it with a classification head operating directly on the compressed latent sequence. The model consists of four components: a dilated convolutional encoder, a vector quantization bottleneck, a recurrent decoder, and a classification head. These components are trained as shown in Figure 1 and are described below.

Each input trajectory window is represented as $X \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$, with T timesteps and F observed features.

The encoder is implemented as a stack of 1D convolutional layers with dilation factors $\{1, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$, enabling the receptive field to grow exponentially with depth. This design captures both short-term motion patterns and longer temporal dependencies.

The vector quantizer uses a codebook of size K , with embedding dimension d . Thus, each timestep is represented by one discrete code index $z_t \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ and its associated embedding vector $q_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$. As a result, the compressed representation of the trajectory is a discrete sequence Z with fixed length T , with one discrete symbol per timestep drawn from a vocabulary of size K . Unlike the original VQ-VAE formulation, which updates the codebook through gradient-based optimization, we employ exponential moving average (EMA) updates. This choice is particularly important for AIS data, where strong class imbalance can cause gradient-based quantization to collapse to a small subset of codes. EMA updates, combined with a dead-code restart mechanism, yield stable training and full codebook utilization.

The decoder reconstructs the input trajectory from the quantized embeddings Q using a two-layer gated recurrent unit (GRU). In addition to Q , positional encodings and auxiliary kinematic features are provided to improve temporal alignment and preserve physically plausible motion patterns. The model therefore learns not only to compress the signal, but also to maintain trajectory structure during reconstruction.

For downstream prediction, classification is performed directly on the discrete sequence Z in the latent space. The quantized embeddings are aggregated through temporal mean pooling and passed to a multilayer perceptron that outputs the activity label y . This design removes the need to reconstruct trajectories during inference, enabling efficient deployment.

Training uses a joint objective that extends the standard VQ-VAE loss with trajectory-consistency and classification terms:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{recon}} + \lambda_{\text{phys}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{dir}} + \lambda_{\text{len}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{len}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{commit}} + \beta(t) \mathcal{L}_{\text{cls}} \quad (7)$$

Here, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{recon}}$ measures reconstruction error, \mathcal{L}_{dir} encourages directional consistency, and \mathcal{L}_{len} penalizes unrealistic changes in traveled distance or speed. The term $\mathcal{L}_{\text{commit}}$ regularizes the encoder–codebook interaction, while \mathcal{L}_{cls} is the supervised classification loss. The scalar $\beta(t)$ follows a warm-up schedule so that the model first learns faithful reconstruction before stronger discriminative supervision is introduced. This is particularly beneficial in imbalanced settings, where early classification gradients may otherwise bias the representation toward the majority class.

IV. EVALUATION

The experiments evaluate the proposed framework along three complementary dimensions: (i) classification performance for vessel activity recognition, (ii) quality and interpretability of the learned discrete representation, and (iii) reconstruction fidelity under strong compression constraints. In addition to comparing against competitive baselines trained on full-resolution trajectories, we analyze codebook utilization and conduct ablation experiments to assess the contribution of the joint training objective.

A. Experimental Setup

The experiments are conducted on the *Fishing Trajectories (AIS)* dataset, publicly available on Kaggle¹. The dataset contains 128 manually annotated vessel trajectories with timestamp-level behavioral labels, providing fine-grained supervision for fishing activity detection. In addition to geographic coordinates, it includes derived motion and contextual attributes such as turning angle, bearing, temporal and spatial gaps, speed, and distance to shore. This combination of raw positional signals and expert annotations makes it a suitable benchmark for evaluating trajectory representation learning and behavior classification methods. After preprocessing, the dataset resulted in 3,824 trajectory windows, each containing 512 timesteps with 5 kinematic features (latitude, longitude, speed-over-ground, course-over-ground, heading). The data is split by original trajectory before window extraction, yielding 3,060 training windows and 764 validation windows. Consequently, no overlapping windows are assigned across sets, and trajectories from the same vessel do not appear in both training and validation data, preventing information leakage. The resulting dataset is highly imbalanced, with two activity classes: fishing (94.6%) and sailing (5.4%). All reported results are computed on the held-out validation set.

The model is trained for 120 epochs using the Adam optimizer with cosine annealing and a batch size of 32. The vector quantizer uses a codebook of size $K = 512$ with embedding dimension $d = 128$, and is updated using exponential moving averages with dead-code restart.

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/thedevastator/detailed-labelled-fishing-trajectories-from-ais>

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed framework: A trajectory window X is encoded by a dilated convolutional network into latent vectors E , which are discretized through nearest-neighbor lookup in a learned codebook \mathcal{C} . The resulting discrete sequence Z forms the compressed representation. Quantized embeddings Q are used by a GRU decoder to reconstruct the trajectory, while the compressed codes are directly used for downstream classification through temporal pooling and an MLP classifier. Training jointly optimizes reconstruction, trajectory-consistency, commitment, and classification objectives.

We compare against three baselines that operate on the full uncompressed signal: a bidirectional GRU, a unidirectional LSTM, and a CNN operating on rendered trajectory images. In contrast, the proposed model performs classification directly on compressed discrete representations.

B. Classification Performance

Table I reports validation performance across all models. The LSTM achieves the strongest baseline performance, with 99.61% accuracy and 98.28% macro F1. The BiGRU performs slightly worse despite its bidirectional structure, suggesting that forward temporal modeling is sufficient for this task. The CNN, which operates only on spatial trajectory images, exhibits a significant drop in macro F1, indicating that temporal and kinematic features are essential for minority-class discrimination.

TABLE I: Validation classification performance.

Model	Acc	Macro F1	Sailing F1
BiGRU	99.21%	96.67%	93.75%
LSTM	99.61%	98.28%	96.77%
CNN	98.30%	92.98%	86.87%
VQ-VAE head	98.95%	95.64%	–

The proposed VQ-VAE classifier achieves 98.95% accuracy and 95.64% macro F1 while operating exclusively on compressed representations. Unlike the baselines, the model simultaneously performs compression and reconstruction, demonstrating that high classification performance can be achieved without access to the raw trajectory.

C. Reconstruction and Compression

The model achieves a mean validation reconstruction error of 7.59 km while compressing each trajectory by up to $17.8\times$. This error is computed as the average point-wise positional deviation along each trajectory and then averaged over the validation set. Given the spatial scale of the dataset, it corresponds to relatively small local deviations rather than structural reconstruction failures. Compression is computed assuming float32 storage for raw features and 16-bit integer storage for code indices, excluding the shared codebook overhead.

These results demonstrate that the discrete representation preserves both geometric fidelity and high-level trajectory structure. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the model accurately reconstructs key trajectory patterns, including turns, loops, and multi-pass structures, despite significant compression.

D. Representation Quality via Linear Probe

To evaluate whether the compressed representation preserves discriminative information independently of the classifier head, we train a logistic regression model on bag-of-codes histograms derived from the discrete latent sequences.

Despite having no access to temporal order or raw trajectory features, the linear probe achieves 99.48% accuracy and 97.64% macro F1, outperforming the trained classifier head. As shown in Fig. 3, the code usage histograms form well-separated clusters in latent space, with sailing trajectories occupying a compact and distinct region. This indicates that the discrete representation itself is highly structured and linearly separable, and that complex classifiers are not required to extract class information.

The improvement over the classifier head is attributed to class imbalance. While the joint model optimizes both recon-

Fig. 2: Representative trajectory reconstructions. The model preserves key geometric structures such as turns, loops, and multi-pass patterns despite significant compression.

struction and classification, the logistic regression is trained with class balancing and focuses entirely on the decision boundary, particularly for the minority class.

E. Codebook Utilization

Codebook utilization is critical for effective discrete representation learning. Table II compares gradient-based and EMA-based quantization under identical conditions.

TABLE II: Codebook utilization comparison.

Method	Active Codes	Utilization
Gradient VQ	16/512	3.1%
EMA VQ	512/512	100%

Gradient-based quantization collapses to a small subset of codes, a known failure mode in imbalanced settings. In contrast, EMA updates combined with dead-code restart maintain full utilization throughout training. This is a key factor enabling the emergence of class-discriminative structure in the latent space. The structure of the learned codebook is illustrated in Fig. 4. Certain codes are highly class-specific, with some activated almost exclusively by sailing trajectories and others by fishing. This demonstrates that the model learns a set of discrete motion primitives, some of which are strongly associated with specific vessel behaviors.

Fig. 3: UMAP projection of code usage histograms over the validation set. Each point corresponds to a trajectory window represented as a 512-dimensional histogram of code frequencies. Fishing trajectories form a diffuse region, while sailing trajectories form a compact and linearly separable cluster, explaining the strong performance of linear classifiers.

F. Ablation Study

To isolate the role of the classification loss, we train a reconstruction-only model ($\beta = 0$) and evaluate the same linear probe on its representations.

TABLE III: Effect of classification loss on representation quality.

Setting	Acc	Macro F1	Sailing F1
Reconstruction only	98.17%	91.90%	84.78%
Joint training	99.48%	97.64%	95.56%

As shown in Table III, even without supervision, the model achieves strong performance, indicating that trajectory reconstruction alone induces meaningful structure in the latent space. However, joint training significantly improves performance, particularly for the minority class (i.e., sailing), where the classification signal sharpens decision boundaries.

This demonstrates that the classification head primarily serves as a training signal that organizes the codebook, while inference can be performed effectively using simpler models.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a VQ-VAE framework for joint compression and classification of AIS trajectories through a shared discrete latent representation. The model achieves high compression while preserving geometric fidelity and behaviorally relevant information, enabling accurate prediction directly from compressed codes.

The learned representation exhibits clear structure, with fishing and sailing trajectories forming separable clusters, supported by the class-specific code activations. The strong

(a) Most exclusive codes per class.

(b) Top-activated codes by class.

Fig. 4: Codebook structure after training. Certain codes are highly class-specific, with some activated almost exclusively by sailing trajectories and others by fishing. High-frequency codes are predominantly associated with the majority class, while a distinct subset captures minority-class behavior.

performance of a simple linear probe further indicates that class information is explicitly encoded in the latent space. The experiments also show that the classification head mainly acts as a training signal, while lightweight models are sufficient at inference time. In addition, EMA-based quantization is essential for stable training, as gradient-based updates lead to severe codebook collapse under class imbalance.

Overall, the results highlight discrete trajectory representations as an efficient interface for large-scale analytics. Although evaluated on AIS data, the framework is general and potentially applicable to other trajectory domains requiring both compact storage and downstream inference. The current evaluation is limited to a relatively small labeled dataset. Future work will assess generalization on larger multi-vessel AIS corpora and stricter vessel-level splits.

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